

Relationship between Access to Mass Media of Cassava Processors and their Socio-Economic Characteristics in Oriire Local Government Area

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Abstract

The study evaluated relationship between access to mass media of cassava processors and their socio-economic characteristics in Oriire Local Government Area. Multistage sampling technique was used to select a total number of 75 respondents that constituted the sample size. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, percentages and frequencies) and logit regression. The mean age of the respondents was 49.06 years. The mean household size was 6 individuals. The assess to mass media in disseminating agricultural information of respondents includes; television (80%), mobile phone (80%), radio (93.33%), radio (50%), internet (42.67%), bulletin (6.67%) and poster (73.33%). The coefficient of age, gender, years of schooling, household size, years of experience and farm size were not statistically significant in relationship with access to mass media. It was concluded that bulletin was the least prominent among assess to mass media utilized in disseminating agricultural information. Therefore, the use of bulletin should be encouraged by the extension agents and their employers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mass media have made their place for backing up agricultural sector through extension activities. Mass media have the capacity to uplift the knowledge and having impact on behaviour (Nazari and Hassan, 2011). The potency of modern electronic technology can be exploited for infotainment of farming community (Guenther and Swan, 2011). The cost of extension advice through mass media comes to be considerably low as compared to individual and group methods. However, the mass media involve one-way communication from information source to the receivers. They permit limited and delayed feedback, which of course is essential for effective communication. Creation of awareness is the first step towards the adoption process (Yawson *et. al.*, 2010). Mass media (electronic & print media) are playing very important role in creating awareness about new agricultural technologies among farmers. Mass media are spreading agricultural technologies to the farmers at a faster rate than personal contacts.

Agricultural extension/information delivery is precisely a process of communication of improved skills, practices, innovations, technologies and knowledge to farmers. Thus, agricultural extension is a service which helps or assists people, particularly farm families through educational procedures in promoting their farming practices and techniques, increasing their production efficiency and income, bettering their levels of living and lifting their social, economic and educational standards of rural life. In many developing countries, wide adoption of research results by majority of farmers remains quite limited. This therefore, calls for a system which allows adequate information flow from researchers to farmers and vice-versa.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Describe socio-economic characteristics of respondents.
2. Assess the respondents assess to mass media for agricultural information dissemination in the study area.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between access to mass media of cassava processors and their socio-economic characteristics

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Oriire Local Government Area, Oyo state, Nigeria. Its headquarters is at Ikoyi Ile. It extends from Ipeba river along Ogbomosho Oyo state to Dogo

junction near Igbeti, headquarters of Olorunsogo Local Government. in Orire Local Government is about 96km, with an area of about 2040 km². The main economic activities of the residents of the towns that make up in Orire Local Government is farming and the main produce from their farming activities are Yam, vegetables, kolanuts, palm oil etc.

The population for this study consists of dry season vegetable farmers in in Orire Local Government Area, Oyo state, Nigeria.

The study used both dependent and independent variables. The dependent variables will be the determinant and it will be dichotomized (yes or no). While the independent variables will include age, sex, educational level, farm size, years of farming experience, etc...

Multistage sampling technique was used to select the respondent. The first stage was the purposive sampling of four villages. The second stage was the proportionate sampling of 20% of registered farmers from each village, thus a total of 75 respondents were interviewed.

Descriptive Statistical Tools that were used were used to describe the socio-economic characteristics and assess to mass media for agricultural information dissemination of respondents and logit was used to test the null hypothesis.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Socio economic characteristics of respondents

Socio economic characteristics of household of respondents were presented below. Most (65.33%) of the cassava processors were males. Thus, cassava processing is dominated by males.

This is probably because cassava processing is labor intensive.

The processors which were less than 40 years of age were 24.76%. Thus, a good number of the respondents were youths. The respondents that were within ages of 40 to 44 years and 45 to 49 years were 4.00% and 21.33% respectively. Also, the respondents that were greater than 50 years of age were 49.91%. Moreover, the mean age of the respondents was 49.06 years. This was an indication that the processors were in their productive age: thus they could be very agile. This could enable them to adopt and diffuse innovative technologies and/or training that could improve their cassava processing.

The respondents had varying religious beliefs. Moreover, their varying religious beliefs could not prevent their adoption and diffusion of innovative technologies and/or training that could improve their cassava processing.

The marital status of respondents were married (84.00%), widowed (9.33%), divorced (4.00%) and single (2.67%). The married category were the main category (84.00%). The married status could encourage the use of household members as cheap cassava processing laborers to the respondents.

The household size of respondents were 3 (12.00%), 4-6 (44.00%) and > 6 (44.00%). The 4-6 and > 6 individual's category were the main category (44.00%) and the mean household size was 6 individuals. This implies that the respondents have very few household members that were depending on them. This could reduce diversion of resource that is meant for household up keeps to cassava processing.

The number of years of farming experience were < 7 (22.67%), 7-12 (25.33%) and > 12 (52.00%). The mean number of years of farming experience was 15 years. This implies that most of the respondents have good farming experience. Experience could improve adoption of improved training on cassava processing.

Farm size were < 2 (28.00%), 2-4 (57.33%) and > 4 (14.67%). The mean farm size was 2.64 hectares. This implies that most of the respondents were small holder farmers.

Table 1: Socio economic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		

Male	49	65.33
Female	26	34.67
Age (years)		
<40	18	24.76
40–44	3	4.00
45–49	16	21.33
>50	38	49.91
Mean = 49.06		
Religion		
Christianity	37	49.33
Islamic	33	44.00
Traditional	5	6.67
Marital Status		
Married	63	84.00
Widowed	7	9.33
Divorced	3	4.00
Single	2	2.67
Household size		
3	9	12.00
4-6	33	44.00
> 6	33	44.00
Mean = 6		

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 1: Socio economic characteristics of respondents (Cont.)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Number of farming experience		
< 7	17	22.67
7-12	19	25.33
> 12	39	52.00
Mean = 15		
Farm size (hectares)		
< 2	21	28.00
2-4	43	57.33
> 4	11	14.67
Mean = 2.64		

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Assess to mass media for agricultural information dissemination

Table 2 presented the assess to mass media in disseminating agricultural information of respondents. The assess to mass media in disseminating agricultural information of respondents includes; television (80%), mobile phone (80%), radio (93.33%), radio (50%), internet (42.67%), bulletin (6.67%) and poster (73.33%). The assess to mass media that was most prominent in disseminating agricultural information was radio. This result implies that radio is the most popular means of disseminating agricultural information in the study area. However, bulletin was the least popular.

Table 2: Assess to mass media in disseminating agricultural information

Mass media Status	Frequency	Percentage
Television		
Yes	60	80.00
No	15	20.00
Mobile phone		
Yes	60	80.00
No	15	20.00
Radio		
Yes	70	93.33
No	5	6.67
Internet		

Yes	32	42.67
No	43	57.33
Bulletin		
Yes	5	6.67
No	70	93.33
Poster		
Yes	55	73.33
No	20	26.67

Source: Field Survey,

Test of Formulated Hypothesis

Table 3: Relationship between access to mass media of cassava processors and their socio-economic characteristics

Dependent variable	Independent variables	Coefficient	P> t
Access to mass media			
	Age	0.022	0.743
	Gender	0.866	0.532
	Years of schooling	0.096	0.440
	Household size	0.555	0.250
	Years of experience	-0.128	0.235
	Farm size	-0.642	0.240
	Constant	1.088	0.638

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

In Table 3, relationship between access to mass media of cassava processors and their socio-economic characteristics was presented. The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between access to mass media of cassava processors and their socio-economic characteristics. The coefficient of Age, gender, years of schooling, household size, years of experience and farm size were not statistically significant in relationship with access to mass media. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between access to mass media of cassava processors and their socio-economic characteristics was not rejected.

Conclusion and Recommendation

It was concluded that bulletin was the least prominent among assess to mass media utilized in disseminating agricultural information. Therefore, the use of bulletin should be encouraged by the extension agents and their employers.

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